

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

Imas Masriah¹, Teti Setiawati²

^{1,2}Pamulang University Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The rapid development of science and technology certainly affects the learning process. Learning outcomes cannot only be seen and measured from how students memorize theories, but can be seen from students' abilities in understanding concepts, in mastering material, in solving problems, and the overall learning outcomes of students. The purpose of this study was to determine whether there was an effect of smartphone use on student learning outcomes in class VIII civics subjects at SMPN 21 Depok. The research method used is quantitative with a correlation approach. The total population for the research target was 227 students, with a total sample of 145 students.

The results of his research show that (1) based on the results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov Smirnov method, a significance value of 0.200 out of 0.05 is obtained, so the data is normally distributed; (2) based on the ANOVA table, the sig. $+0.070 < 0.05$, then the criteria meet linearity; (3) based on the results of the Regression Determination Test, an R Square value of 0.097 or 9 is obtained.7%. This shows that the use of smartphones has an effect of 9.7% on learning outcomes, while the remaining 90.3% is influenced by other variables not examined in this research; and (4) based on the t test (Partial Test), variable X has a value of $1.822 > 1.655$ and with a significance of variable X of $0.070 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that it is accepted while rejected, which means that smartphone use has a positive correlation with learning outcomes in subjects PPKn. $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel}$, so H_a accept.

KEYWORDS: Smartphone Use, Student Learning Outcomes, PPKn

INTRODUCTION

A. Background

Education is one of the foundations in the progress of a nation, where the better the quality of education in a nation, the better the quality of the nation. In Indonesia, education is highly respected, because education has a very important role in the realization of a dignified national civilization. Because in Indonesia education is very, very important, therefore the purpose of education is regulated clearly and in detail in the National Education System Law Number 20 of 2003 which reads: National Education Goals develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God Almighty. Almighty, having noble character, being healthy, knowledgeable, capable of being creative, independent, and being a democratic and responsible citizen.

According to Hidayat et al(2019, p. 23) Education is a conscious and planned effort to provide guidance or assistance in developing the physical and spiritual potential given by adults to students to achieve maturity and achieve goals so that students are able to carry out their life tasks independently.

Along with the times and after 76 years of independent Indonesia, Indonesian education has made more progress, even now the government requires 12 years of education for Indonesian citizens with the aim of educating the nation's life, as well as providing the widest possible opportunities for Indonesian citizens. In fact, to promote Indonesian education, the government provides a special education budget in the form of BOS (School Operational Assistance), provides scholarships for education students such as the Indonesia Smart Card (KIP), and the Jakarta Smart Card (KJP) specifically for residents of the capital city of Jakarta, provides training to teachers. to improve the quality of education, and guarantee the cost of education (free schooling) in certain areas, especially elementary and junior high schools.

According to Saputra et All (2016, p. 3) Pancasila and Citizenship Education (PPKn) is one of the subjects taught at the SMP/MTs level, which is designed to produce students who have faith and noble character as directed by the nation's philosophy of life. Indonesia, namely Pancasila so that it can act as an effective and responsible citizen. The discussion in the study as a whole covers the four pillars of nationality which are related to one another, namely Pancasila, the 1945 Constitution, the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and Bhinneka Tunggal Ika. Meanwhile, according to Samsuri (2012, p. 28) PPN can be interpreted as preparation for the younger generation (students) or the nation's successors to be able to become citizens who have the knowledge, skills.

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

The results of students in learning Civics can not only be measured by how much value they get on the exam, or how much theory they can memorize, but can be seen and measured by the ability of students to understand concepts, mastery of material, and solve problems. , and overall student learning outcomes for 1 semester.

Each student certainly has a different comprehension power when learning Civics in class, students who are active and tend to focus will certainly be more responsive in understanding the learning material conveyed by the teacher in class. In contrast to students who are passive and less focused when Civics learning takes place, of course they will experience difficulties in understanding learning. Therefore, as a teacher, you must be able to innovate in conveying learning in class in order to build enthusiasm and focus on students when learning takes place. Of course, the teacher can do this with various learning models and combined with modern learning and using internet-based technology.

Moreover, education in the 21st century now is more emphasized on knowledge skills, skills and attitudes as well as mastery of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). ICT advances that are happening at this time have changed the paradigm of learning and learning. The old paradigm that considers the teacher as the only source of information in the learning process is no longer valid today. According to Benny (2020. P, 10) The rapid development of ICT has changed teachers no longer have to act as teachers, centers of information and knowledge resources alone, but also become managers and develop learning programs that can help students or learners achieve the skills or competencies needed. Meanwhile, according to Sitepu (2017. p, 28) The progress of ICT produces various types and appearance of media that can be used for learning purposes which makes teachers and textbooks or printed media, as well as nature no longer the dominating learning resource. Because from now on and in the future there will be various technology-based learning resources whose abilities can rival the abilities of a teacher, print media and also nature.

ICT itself is a technology that includes electronic devices, computers, laptops, note books, smartphones or gadgets and telecommunication, which includes software that can be used to create, translate and manipulate information in various forms. Along with the very rapid development of ICT, Indonesia is also taking advantage of this ICT development in the health sector, the telecommunications sector, the economic sector and also the education sector.

In today's era of globalization, almost all groups, from children, adolescents, to the elderly, are familiar with super-sophisticated tools or technology that can be used to easily and quickly access information from any part of the world. call it gadgets. Gadgets are today's technological developments that target all groups, from children to adults. The gadget here is a communication tool that has many functions, where these functions already use different features for each model and type. Gadgets in a general sense are considered as an electronic device that has a special function for each device. Examples include computers, laptops, note books, smartphones and so on.

According to Hilir(2021, p. 3) the use of gadgets, especially smartphones that are connected to the internet network, has a very positive impact on the world of education if used wisely. The internet is one of the communication media that really attracts students' interest in the learning material that will be delivered by the teacher.

Indonesian smartphone users are also growing rapidly. Digital marketing research institute Emarketer estimates that by 2018 the number of active smartphone users in Indonesia will be more than 100 million people. With such a large number, Indonesia will become the country with the fourth largest number of active smartphone users in the world after China, India and America. The Ministry of Communication and Informatics stated that internet usage in Indonesia is very high. This is driven by cheap internet rates, and the large number of smartphone users reaching 167 million people or 89% of Indonesia's total population.

Market research company IDC released its third quarter (Q3) 2020 smartphone shipment report. In its report, IDC revealed that there was a 49 percent growth in smartphone usage compared to the previous quarter, and 21 percent from the same period last year. As quoted from the IDC report, Friday (27/11/2020) this increase was partly due to activities such as Distance Learning (PJJ) which drove a strong recovery in Q3 2020.

In 2021, the Hootsuite (We are Social) Indonesian Digital Report released data and trends regarding the internet and social media on February 11, which contained:

1. The 2021 World Internet and Social Media User Trend Data Report in the World is as follows.

Figure 1. Internet and social media user trend data for 2021 around the world Information :

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

- a. Total Population (total population): 7.83 billion
- b. Unique Mobile Users: 5.22 billion (66.6% of the world's population)
- c. Internet users: 4.66 billion (59.5% of the world's population)
- d. Active Social Media Users: 4.20 billion (53.6% of the world's population).

2. Data Report on Internet and Social Media User Trends in Indonesia for 2021

Figure 2. Trend data for internet and social media users in 2021 in Indonesia Information:

- a. Total Population (total population): 274.9 million
- b. Unique Mobile Users: 345.3 million (125.6% of the total population in Indonesia)
- c. Internet users: 202.6 million (73.7% of the total population in Indonesia)
- d. Active Social Media Users: 170 million (61.8% of the total population in Indonesia)

3. Time spent accessing Indonesian digital media

Meanwhile, in accessing the media, Smartphone users who are connected to the internet in Indonesia spend varying amounts of time, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 3. Time Used to Access Digital Media Information :

- a. Average daily time on the internet via any device: 8 hours, 52 minutes.
- b. Average daily television viewing time (broadcast, streaming and video on demand): 2 hours, 50 minutes.
- c. Average daily time on social media via any device: 3 hours, 41 minutes.
- d. Average daily time to listen to music 1 hour, 30 minutes.
- e. The average daily time spent listening to the radio is 33 minutes
- f. The average daily time spent listening to podcasts is 44 minutes
- g. Average daily game play time: 1 hour, 16 minute

4. Social Media Platforms that are Widely Used in Indonesia 2021

The percentage of internet users using each social media platform [survey-based] is shown in the figure below:

Figure 4. Widely Used Social Media Platforms Information :

- a. Youtube users in Indonesia are 93.8% of the total population.
- b. Whatsapp users in Indonesia are 87.7% of the total population.
- c. Instagram users in Indonesia are 86.6% of the total population.

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

- d. Facebook users in Indonesia are 85.5% of the total population.
- e. Twitter users in Indonesia are 63.6%
- f. Facebook Messenger users in Indonesia are 52.4%
- g. Line users in Indonesia are 44.3%
- h. Likeidn users in Indonesia are 39.4%
- i. Tiktok users in Indonesia are 38.7%
- j. Pinterest users in Indonesia are 35.6%
- k. Telegram users in Indonesia are 28.5%
- l. Wechat users in Indonesia are 26.2%
- m. Snapchat users in Indonesia are 25.4%
- n. Skype users in Indonesia are 24.3%
- o. Tumblr users in Indonesia are 18.4%
- p. Reddit users in Indonesia are 17.1%

Smartphones is a mobile phone that has the ability to use and function like a computer. A smartphone can also be interpreted as a mobile phone that works using operating system (OS) software that provides standard and basic relationships for application developers. There are also those who define a smartphone as a smart mobile phone that has advanced features such as Email, Internet, ebook readers and others. In short, a smartphone is a small computer that has the capability of a telephone (Destiana, 2019, p. 193). Meanwhile, according to Aziz & Nuraniah(2018, p.21). The smartphone is the leading device taking on and playing the role of a universal mobile terminal.

According to Fatimah (2014. p, 83) smartphones are able to make one of the interesting learning media, because students can learn material in different ways, namely using smartphones as learning resources. In addition to making learning more interesting, students can study material without being limited in time, meaning that students can study outside of learning hours, so that it will have a positive impact on students in using cellphones/smartphones as learning tools.

According to Early(2018, p. 305). The use of smartphones connected to the internet makes it easy to access information and find various references to support the learning process. So that when they get assignments from the teacher, students can get a lot of information about the subject matter so that it will increase their knowledge and can improve their learning outcomes.

So it can be concluded that the higher the use of smartphones used for learning at school, it will be able to help increase student knowledge and improve student learning outcomes.

The correct use of smartphones really helps students to seek and explore knowledge easily and quickly, of course. The information you want to look for can be accessed anywhere and anytime you want if you really need it. Based on the 2020 Newzo research report, Indonesia is ranked 4th with 160.23 million smartphone users, after the United States, India, and the first position is occupied by China, which has reached 911.9 million smartphone users. However, it is very unfortunate that in our country the use of smartphones for students cannot be used wisely as they should, students tend to use these smartphones for things that are not actually required at their age. The smartphones they have are generally only used to access social media such as WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, playing online games, listening to music, watching audio-visual services, and so on. Even though basically parents give smartphones to children because they think that smartphones are easy to use to learn to read, write, count and other things to support children's learning processes because in addition to many educational applications and games that can make children smarter, smartphones are also given so that children don't often play outside the house and can take advantage of studying at home using a smartphone. But the fact is that the use of smartphones by children cannot be used by them as they should, even children tend to only play online games and play social media without opening information and applications that support their learning. This right is actually clear that giving children a smartphone not only has a positive impact but also a negative impact, of course.

In this day and age, where the development of technology is so fast, some schools and teachers allow their students to use smartphones in the school environment with the aim that students can access new knowledge easily and quickly, but there are also schools that do not allow the use of smartphones in the school environment. and classes with the aim that students can concentrate during the learning process takes place. The teaching and learning process is the main activity in schools. A teacher always wants and expects his students to succeed in the learning process. The success of the teaching and learning process is always accompanied by maximum efforts from both the teacher and the students themselves, of course. The teacher must seek methods and use interesting media in the teaching and learning process so that students do not feel bored in the learning process besides that the goal is that students are not easily bored with the ongoing learning process. But besides the teacher's efforts, students must also be enthusiastic and more active in the learning process in order to increase motivation and learning outcomes, of course.

Gadgets that are widely used by students at school are cellphones. This electronic tool has many benefits, ranging from communication, online games, to its use to seek knowledge and information from around the world. The use of mobile phones for

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

students will greatly affect their learning outcomes if used properly to support the learning process, because in essence with smartphones, students are expected to be able to overcome the limitations of knowledge and information that they have not received and have not been explained by the teacher at school.

Learning is a process of effort that is carried out by a person to obtain changes in new behavior as a whole, as a result of his own experience in interaction with his environment. So, in every learning process there must be something that changes, both in terms of knowledge, behavior, perceptions and so on. While learning outcomes are changes that occur in students, which involve cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects as a result of learning activities.

Based on the results of the researchers' study regarding the learning outcomes of the PPKn subject, it was also quite low because it did not reach the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM) score of 75. The following is data on the final semester final week (PAS) results for Class VIII PPKn subjects which will be held online on December 6, 2021 at SMPN 21 Depok

Table 1. The average value (Mean) of PAS PPKn Class VIII

No	Class	Average Score (Mean)
1	VIII-1	50
2	VIII-2	54
3	VIII-3	56
4	VIII-4	52
5	VIII-5	53
6	VIII-6	56
7	VIII-7	59

Resultsthe average value of PAS class VIII in PPKn SMPN 21 Depok subjects can be seen in the following pie chart:

Figure 5. Diagram of the average value of PAS Class VIII

Based on the diagram above, it can be interpreted that the average score of PAS PPKn class VIII-1 is 14% in number 50, class VIII-2 is 14% in number 54, class VIII-3 is 15% in number 56, class VIII-4 is 13% in number 52, class VIII-5 is 14% in number 53, class VIII-6 is 15% in number 56, and class VIII-7 is 15% in number 59.

Preliminary observations made by researchers were that students at SMPN 21 Depok did not pay close attention to the presentation material presented by the PPKn subject teachers, there were some students who were engrossed in playing games in class during the learning process. From these observations the impact of using smartphones will cause students to be unprepared to accept the subject matter that will be conveyed by the teacher if some of the students are still playing smartphones secretly. This happens due to a lack of supervision and restrictions on the use of smartphones by parents and teachers.

This research is not the only research that has been carried out, as in previous studies that have previously been conducted to examine and examine the Effect of Intensity Smartphone Use on Learning Outcomes. Research conducted by Nur Syamsiah, (2020) entitled The Influence of Smartphone Use Intensity and Learning Motivation on Student Learning Outcomes in Class VIII at MTS Negeri 7 Malang. The results of his research show that there is a positive relationship between smartphone use and learning motivation with student learning outcomes at MTS Negeri 7 Malang.

From the explanation above, it can be understood that student independence in learning is one of the important factors that must get more attention so that learning outcomes are more satisfying. Therefore, researchers consider it important to examine the effect of smartphone use on learning outcomes.

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Approach and Methodology

1. Approach

Based on the problems and research objectives that have been stated above, this research was designed to obtain information and find out "The Influence of Smartphone Use on Student Learning Outcomes in Civics Subjects at SMPN 21 Depok" so this research uses a quantitative approach, namely looking at the influence between variables -The variable studied is the independent variable using a smartphone (Variable X) and the dependent variable is the learning outcomes of students in Civics subjects (Bound Variable).

2. Research methods

The method used in this study is the correlation method which is a research method that aims to determine the effect or relationship between two or more variables.

Figure 6. Independent variable and dependent variable t

B. Population and Sample

1. Target Population

- a. In this study, the target population was students at SMPN 21 Depok, Jl. Muhajir No 98-111, Gandul, Cinere District, Depok City, West Java which consists of 7 classes, namely class VIII-1, VIII-2, VIII-3, VIII-4, VIII-5 VIII-6 and VIII-7 which a total of 227 students, in the 2021-2022 Academic Year.

Table 2. Total Target Population

No	Class	Gender		Amount
		Man	Woman	
1	VIII-1	12	20	32
2	VIII-2	16	16	32
3	VIII-3	15	18	33
4	VIII-4	15	16	31
5	VIII-5	14	19	33
6	VIII-6	15	18	33
7	VIII-7	19	13	33
Total				227

2. Sample

According to Sugiyono (2015, p.83) the sample is part of the population. For this reason, the sample taken from the population must be truly representative. Sampling technique was used *purposive sampling*, where sampling is based on certain considerations. In this study the sample amounted to 227 people. With the sample formula most often used in research, namely the Slovin formula. The Slovin formula is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + (Ne)^2}$$

Information :

1 = Constant

N = Number of Samples

n = Total Population

e = Error (5% that can be tolerated for the inaccuracy of using the sample as a replacement for the population.

The way according to slovin:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+(Ne)^2}$$

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

$$n = \frac{227}{1+227(0,05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{227}{1+227(0,0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{227}{1,5675}$$

$$n = \frac{227}{1,56}$$

$$n = 145,512$$

Rounded up to 145

So the sample in this study was 145 students, consisting of 7 classes. Based on the calculations from the Slovin formula, the number of respondents was 145 students. Furthermore, a sample of respondents is selected proportionally from each sample. According to Juliandi et al. (2014) Proportional Random Sampling is sampling from a population that has different groups and characteristics. In proportional random sampling, each class in the population has the opportunity to be sampled. Proportional is used to determine the number of samples in each class.

The proportional random sampling formula is:

$$N_i = \frac{n_i}{n} \times n$$

Information:

n_i = Size of each sample stratum (People)

N_i = Size of each population stratum (People)

N = Total population size (Persons)

n = Total sample size (Persons)

Table 3. Sample Distribution using Proportional Random Sampling

No	Class	Distribution of Number of Samples
1	VIII-1	$\frac{32}{227} \times 145 = 21$
2	VIII-2	$\frac{32}{227} \times 145 = 21$
3	VIII-3	$\frac{33}{227} \times 145 = 21$
4	VIII-4	$\frac{31}{227} \times 145 = 19$
5	VIII-5	$\frac{33}{227} \times 145 = 21$
6	VIII-6	$\frac{33}{227} \times 145 = 21$
7	VIII-7	$\frac{33}{227} \times 145 = 21$
Amount		145

Based on Proportional Random Sampling calculations, 21 students were obtained in class VIII-1, 21 students in class VIII-2, 21 students in class VIII-3, 19 students in class VIII-4, 21 students in class VIII-5, class VIII-6 21 students and class VIII-7 21 students SMPN 21 Depok.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Research result

1. Normality test

As explained in the previous chapter, this study used regression and correlation analysis techniques. This technique can be used if the data for each research variable is normally distributed.

The normality of the two pairs of research variable data, namely *Smartphone use*(X) with Learning Outcomes (Y), carried out using the computer program SPSS for MS Windows Release 25 by using the Kolmogorov Smirnof normality test with the following statistical hypothesis formulation:

H_0 : Population data is normally distributed

H_1 : Population data is not normally distributed

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

Table 4. Normality test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residuals
N		145
Normal Parameters, b	Means	,0000000
	std. Deviation	9,45877396
Most Extreme Differences	absolute	,064
	Positive	,064
	Negative	-.054
Test Statistics		,064
asypm. Sig. (2-tailed)		,200c,d
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.		
d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.		

Based on the results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov Smirnov method, a significance value of 0.200 was obtained >from 0.05, so the datanormally distributed. Because it is normally distributed, the results of the analysis can be continued to the next stage.

2. Correlation Regression Analysis

Linear Equation Test

The linear equation test was carried out using the SPSS for Windows Relation 25 computer program, the results are as follows:

Table 5. Linear Equation Results

Coefficients a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	std. Error	Betas		
1	(Constant)	37,843	10.106		3,744	,000
	Smartphone_Use	,329	,180	,151	1,822	,070

a. Dependent Variable: Learning_Results

Based on the calculation results above, the Linear Regression equation for the effect of X on Y is obtained, namely:

$$\hat{Y} : a + bX$$

$$\hat{Y} : 37.843 + 0.329$$

The Linear regression equation above has the following interpretation:

- a) Constant (a) of 37.843 indicates that if the change in the independent variable is considered constant or) (zero), then the value of Learning Outcomes (Y) is 37.843

Smartphone use variable (X) is 0.329 and has a positive sign. This means that every use of a smartphone will increase learning outcomes by 0.329. This means that the greater the use of a smartphone, the learning outcomes will increase.

a. Linearity Test

Linearity test was carried out using *computer SPSS for MS Windows Release 25*, the results are as follows:

Table 6. Linearity Results

ANOVA a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	585,839	1	585,839	3,321	,070b
	residual	25222,823	143	176,383		
	Total	25808,662	144			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning_Results
b. Predictors: (Constant), Smartphone_Use

Based on the calculation results above, the ANOVA table above determines the level of significance or literacy and regression. If the significance value is <0.005 then the regression model is linear. Based on the table above, the sig value of +0.070 <0.05 is obtained. Then the criteria meet linearity.

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

b. Regression Determination Test

The regression determination test was carried out using the SPSS for Windows Relation 25 computer program, the results are as follows:

Table 7. Regression Determination Test Results

Summary model b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	std. Error of the Estimate
1	,311a	,097	,091	5.019
a. Predictors: (Constant), Smartphone_Use				
b. Dependent Variable: Learning_Results				

Based on the table above, it explains how much the variation in the value of Y is caused by X, from the calculation results above, the R Square is 0.097 or 9%. This shows that Usesmartphones gives an effect of 9.7% on learning outcomes, while the remaining 90.3% is influenced by variables not examined in this study.

c. Correlation Coefficient Test

The correlation coefficient test was carried out using the SPSS for Windows Relation 25 computer program, the results are as follows:

Table 8. Correlation Coefficient Results

correlations			
		Smartphone_Use	Learning outcomes
Smartphone_Use	Pearson Correlation	1	,004
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,959
	N	145	145
Learning outcomes	Pearson Correlation	,004	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,959	
	N	145	145

Based on table 4.11, the correlation between Smartphone Use and Learning Outcomes has a positive direction, with a correlation coefficient of 0.004. So it can be concluded that there is a positive relationship with variable (X) usage *smartphone* to variable (Y) Learning Outcomes. This means that the higher the Smartphone Use score, the higher the Learning Outcome score.

d. T Test (Partial Test)

The T test (Partial Test) is an individual partial coefficient test that is used to find out whether the independent variable (X) individually affects the dependent variable (Y), Based on the significance value of the SPSS output results:

- 1) If the Sig value < 0.05 then the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable
- 2) If the Sig value > 0.05 then the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable.

Testing the hypothesis with $\alpha = 5\%$ (using 2 sides so the significance value is 0.05%), while the degrees of freedom testing $nk = 145 - 1 - 1$, in this case the value t_{tabel} table is 0.05: 143 then the value is 1.655. The following is the result of testing the hypothesis using the t test (partial test). t_{tabel}

Table 9. t test (Partial Test)

Coefficientsa						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	std. Error	Betas		
1	(Constant)	37,843	10.106		3,744	,000
	Smartphone_Use	,329	,180	,151	1,822	,070
a. Dependent Variable: Learning_Results						

From the results of the output above, it can be concluded as follows:

Relationship of Smartphone Use (X) to Learning Outcomes (Y).

Based on the test in table 4.12, variable X has a value of 1.822 > 1.655 and with a significance of variable X of 0.070 > 0.05, it can be concluded that accepted and rejected means that the use of smartphones has a positive correlation with learning outcomes in Civics Subjects at SMPN 21 Depok. $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}, H_a H_o$

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

B. Discussion

- 1) The use of smartphones on learning outcomes using simple regression and correlation. From the calculations obtained $a = 37.843$ and $b = 0.329$. By substituting the values a and b into the regression equation, a simple linear equation is obtained $= 37.843 + 0.329X$
- 2) The results of calculating the use of smartphones (X) on learning outcomes (Y) are indicated by a correlation coefficient of 0.151. This means that the higher the Smartphone Use score, the higher the Learning Outcome score level.
- 3) To test the significance of the Correlation Coefficient (Y) over (X) it is carried out with a T test. If thing $< t_{\text{tabel}}$ then H_a is rejected H_o is accepted and if it is then H_a is accepted H_o is rejected. The T-test in this study resulted in a time of 1.822 while the T-test at a significant level of 0.05 was 1.655. Thus there is a positive correlation between Smartphone Use and Learning Outcomes, this shows that the higher the use of a smartphone, the higher the level of Learning Outcomes.
- 4) The coefficient of determination (r) between Smartphone Use and Learning Outcomes in Civics Subjects can be explained from Smartphone use with Learning Outcomes of 9.7%.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion cant concluded that there is positive and significant effect of Smartphone use on Civic Education Learning Outcomes in SMPN 21 Depok students West Java Indonesia. This is evidenced from the results of the Regression Determination Test obtained $Y = 37.834 + 0.329 X$ sig value = $0.070 < 0.05$ and $1.822 > 0.050$, there is a positive and significant influence indicating that the contribution of Smartphone Use (X) to Learning Outcomes (Y) of the value R Square of 0.097 or 9.7%. ($t_{\text{hitung}} > t_{\text{tabel}}$).

Thus there are still 90.3% which are still influenced by other factors that are not examined by researchers. This shows that Use *smartphones* gives an effect of 9.7% on learning outcomes, while the remaining 90.3% is influenced by other variables not examined in this research.

B. Suggestion

- 1) For school principals, with the results of this study, researchers suggest that school principals hold more activities such as seminars and training on the importance of using smartphones for learning media.
- 2) For teachers, with the results of this study, researchers suggest that they use a variety of learning methods based on smartphone technology.
- 3) For students, with the results of this study, the researchers suggest increasing the use of smartphones as learning media both at school and at home.

REFERENCES

- 1) A, Benny. (2017). Media & Technology in Learning.
- 2) Afandi, M., Chamalah, E., & Oktarina Puspita Wardani. (2009). Numerical solutions for non-Markovian stochastic equations of motion. In Computer Physics Communications (Vol. 180, Issue 4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2008.12.005>
- 3) Alwafi Ridho Subarkah. (2018). Use of Gadgets on Student Learning Outcomes, 151(2), 10–17.
- 4) Aziz, M., & Nurainiah, N. (2018). The Effect of Mobile Phone Use on Adolescent Social Interaction in Dayah Meunara Village, Kutamakmur District, North Aceh District. Effects of Mobile Phone Use on Adolescent Social Interaction, 4(2), 19–39. <https://doi.org/10.22373/al-ijtimaiyyah.v4i1.4204>
- 5) Berry, M., & Schleser, M. (2014). Mobile media making in an age of smartphones. In Mobile Media Making in an Age of smartphones. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137469816>
- 6) David, D. (2019). Application of Educational Data Mining to Predict Learning Outcomes of SMAK Ora et Labora Students. Journal of Computer Science, 12(2), 73. <https://doi.org/10.24843/jik.2019.v12.i02.p02>
- 7) Destiana. (2019). The Influence of Android-Based Information Technology (Smartphone) in Industry 4.0 Education. Proceedings of the National Education Seminar for Postgraduate Programs at Pgr University, Palembang, 190–197.
- 8) Early, NPA (2018). The Influence of Smartphone Use and Learning Motivation on Learning Outcomes in Economics Subjects in Class Xi Iis at SMA Negeri 1 Mojosari. Journal of Economic Education (JUPE), 6(3), 349–354.
- 9) Etty Sofyatiningrum, M.Ed Dr. Etty Sisdiana Ikhya Ulumuddin, mpd Fransisca Nur'Aini, S.Si Apt., MPP Hamdan Sugilar, MP (2020). Anthology of Teacher Feedback on Student Learning Processes and Outcomes. Center for Policy Research, Agency for Research and Development and Bookkeeping, Ministry of Education and Culture. <https://puslitjakdikbud.kemdikbud.go.id>
- 10) Garcia-swartz, m. C. -k. DD (1967). From mainframes to smartphones. In angewandte chemie international edition, 6(11), 951–952. (vol. 13, april issue).

The Influence of Smartphone Use on Students Learning Outcomes in Ppkn Subjects at Smpn 21 Depok West Java Indonesia

- 11) Ginting, E., & Permana, Y. (2018). Pedagogy: Assessment Evaluation of Learning Processes and Outcomes. 1–77.
- 12) Haikal, MF, Thohari, MI, & Mustafida, F. (2018). *The Influence of Using Smartphones on the Learning Achievement of Mts Hasyim Asyari Students in Batu City*. *Journal of Islamic Education*, 3, 196–202.
- 13) Hendri, h., Khoiri, m., Jaya, h. W., & Masriah, i. (2021). *Promotion of humane social media for teachers and parents of students*. *citizenship Journal*, 5(2), 552-560.
- 14) Hilir., A. (2021). Educational Technology in the Digital Age.
- 15) Masriah, I., Sumantri, W., Syafi'i, S., Fajriyah, S., Safrudin, E., & Utari, p. DS (2021). Implementation of the use of information and communication technology in the learning management system during the Covid-19 pandemic at the Nurul Amal Islamic Education Foundation. *Padma journal: community dharma service*, 1(2).
- 16) Masriah, i. (2019). Entrepreneurship knowledge relationship with the effectiveness of school-based management (MBS). *Feasible scientific journal (jif)*, 1(1), 14-21.
- 17) Ministry of Education and Culture. (1982). Introduction and Aim of the Study. *Acta Pædiatrica*, 71, 6–6.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1651-2227.1982.tb08455.x>
- 18) Musrifa Arshad. (2019). The Influence of Smartphones on Student Learning Outcomes at MTS Negeri Lasalimu. I(1), 57–72.
- 19) Najichun, M. (2016). The Relationship between Students' Perceptions of Mathematics Teachers and Students' Mathematics Learning Outcomes. *Undip Journal of Psychology*, 15(2), 143–150.
- 20) Pmpk.kemdikbud.go.id. (2003). Law (UU) No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System [JDIH BPK RI]. Indonesian Education System, 37. <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Home/Details/43920/uu-no-20-tahun-2003>
- 21) PPKN.2022."According to Experts", <https://ppkn.co.id/pengertian-pkn-menurut-paraahli/#:~:text=Pengertian%20PPKN%20According%20Para%20Ahli%20PPKN.CO.ID%20E2%80%93%20Mata,for%20can%20develop%20country%20aswell%20also%20nation%20Indonesia>. Accessed on 04 August 2022 at 08.39 WIB
- 22) Rahmat Hidayat, & Serve. (2019). Rahmat Hidayat & Abdillah's Educational Science Book.
- 23) Reza, Muhammad. 2022. "The Understanding of Pancasila and Citizenship Education"
<https://www.mandandi.com/2022/01/pengertian-dinding-pancasila-dan.html>. Retrieved 04 August 2022
- 24) Sanjaya, W. (2010). *Education Standards Oriented Learning Strategy*. Jakarta: Kencana
- 25) Sari, MI (2018). The Effect of Using Gadgets on Motivation and Learning Outcomes of Class V Students Mi Thoriqotussa'Adah Pujon Malang Regency. <http://etheses.uin-malang.ac.id/13392/1/14140053.pdf>
- 26) Sutrisno. (2021). Increasing Interest and Learning Outcomes in Tik Topology Material Network with Learning Media. In *Expertmedia Press (IKAPI Member: 264/JTI/2020)* (p. 22).
[https://books.google.co.id/books?Id=v1uneaaqbaj&pg=PA10&dq=pengertian+minat+menurut+para+ahli&hl=id&sa=X&ved=2ahukewi17ml-7druahwd4nmbhbaqv8q6aewaxoecaag#v=onepage&q=definition of interest according to experts&f=false](https://books.google.co.id/books?Id=v1uneaaqbaj&pg=PA10&dq=pengertian+minat+menurut+para+ahli&hl=id&sa=X&ved=2ahukewi17ml-7druahwd4nmbhbaqv8q6aewaxoecaag#v=onepage&q=definition%20of%20interest%20according%20to%20experts&f=false)
- 27) Sudjana, Nana. 2005. *Assessment of Teaching and Learning Process Results*. Bandung. Rosdakarya youth.
- 28) Suprijono, Agus. 2015 *Cooperative Learning*. Yogyakarta: Learning Library
- 29) Syaiful bahri. Djamarah. 2008 *Secrets of Learning Success*. Jakarta. PT Rinaka Cipta
- 30) Tiara Dewi, Muhammad Amir Masruhim, RS (2016). Theory Study and Thinking Framework a. *Smartphone Usage Indicator*, April, 5–24.
- 31) Wirda, Y., Ulumudin, I., Widiputera, F., Listiawati, N., & Fujianita, S. (2020). The determinant factors of student learning outcomes.
- 32) Zaenudidin.2022. Theory of Learning Outcomes & Indicators of Learning Outcomes According to Experts.
https://artikelsiana.com/teori-hasil-belajar-indikator-hasil-belajar-menurut-para-ahli/#Indikator_Hasil_Belajar. Accessed on 16 February 2022 at 23.05 WIB.